

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP8

Italian Pilot

Deliverable D8.2

Pilot set-up & test specifications

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternate Current
AFE	Active Front End
AFE	Active Front End
API	Application Programming Interface
DC	Direct Current
DMUs	DC Measurement Units
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EV	Electric Vehicle
EPES	Electrical Power and Energy System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HV	High Voltage
IT	Information Technology
LV	Low Voltage
MV	Medium Voltage
PMUs	Phasor Measurement Units
PS	Primary Substation
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RP	Resolution Plan
RPF	Reverse Power Flow
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SS	Secondary Substation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Over the years, the distribution grid has changed considerably. Today, the great production of energy by Renewable Energy Sources that produce fluctuating power into the distribution grid requires a greater ability to manage the low voltage section of the grid, since energy producers and users are more and more connected to the low voltage grid. Today the role of the power grid customer, whether producer, user, or prosumer, is central in the sustainable and reliable management of a modern distribution grid.

The HYPERRIDE project in the Italian pilot develops a hybrid Alternate Current(AC)/Direct Current (DC) distribution grid that matches the needs of AC and DC users/prosumers with the needs of Distribution System Operator (DSO) to limit congestions at the nodes of the grid and promote the local consumption of the energy self-produced. The achievement of this synergy is based on flexibility criteria provided by the grid customers. Flexibility in consumption and production by the customers increases the sustainability and resilience of the grid as a whole, with impact mainly on Low Voltage (LV) grid but with benefits also on Medium Voltage (MV) grid at an upper level of hierarchy in the power grid. The effect of local variations in the hybrid AC/DC grid will be related to the effects on the entire grid, including the MV section.

The selection of DC/DC and AC/DC converters, hybrid grid architecture, protections, monitoring and control systems is based on reliability and multi-operability requirements of all the systems involved. The pilot performance evaluation will be related to the fixed objectives in order to detect the deviations from the expected results and if necessary implement corrective actions and different settings in the equipment operating thresholds. The modern conventional grid is by nature a dynamic and adaptive system, the hybrid grid is even more so. The adaptive behaviour of the AC/DC hybrid distribution grid is in compliance with the requirements of the existing real AC distribution grid to improve the reliability of the whole system and therefore supply better services to the grid customers. The pilot set-up and test specification sets the Use Cases requirements to achieve and evaluate the synergy between all systems involved in the project. The impact of the new DC grid will be also evaluated in the real distribution grid operation.

The definition of the pilot setup and test specifications is the result of a close collaboration with Work Package (WP) 2 and the identification of three use cases to test the integration requirements and validate them in a real distribution grid where coexist electric vehicle charging systems, Photovoltaic (PV) power plants, storage systems, critical loads and a DC system control infrastructure dedicated to the pilot. In addition, all required additional equipment including sensors, AC controllers, Application Programming Interface (API) and other hardware modules implemented or existing in the pilot will be tested.

Table 1: Italian Pilot – Use Cases.

<i>Use case identification</i>		
<i>ID</i>	<i>Area Domain(s)/ Zone(s) –(SGAM model)</i>	<i>Name of use case</i>
HYPERRIDE-UC-ITALIAN-001	DER/OPERATION	Forming an Energy Community
HYPERRIDE-UC-ITALIAN-002	DISTRIBUTION/STATION	Provide flexibility to the grid operator (DSO)
HYPERRIDE-UC-ITALIAN-003	DER/OPERATION	Efficient Fault Management in Grid Operation

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This deliverable will provide a description of the trial site as feedback to HYPERRIDE system designers, along with use case evaluation criteria, test and certification procedures of the pilot. The report will also describe the procedures and the installation program of new equipment.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 introduces the context where the hybrid AC/DC grid is implemented, taking into account the needs of the existing grid in order to improve its performances. Furthermore, the new DC architecture is introduced, together with the requirements for its integration in the pilot. Section 3 deals with the systems setup starting from the analysis of three use cases chosen for the Italian Pilot. Section 4 settles on the physical parameters and their measurement criteria to evaluate the impact of the hybrid grid in the complexity of the distribution district. Section 5 is on the conclusion of the report.

2 Power Grid

2.1 General Data

The power grid of Terni serves a city and some villages for a total of about 100,000 inhabitants. Its main characteristics are reassumed in the following Figure 1:

• Surface of the Municipality of Terni served by the Power Grid	211 km ²
• Distribution Grid overall length	
• MV	650 km
• LV	1400 km
• HV/MV Primary Substation	Nr. 3 (Terni Ovest, Ex Sit, Villa Valle)
• MV/LV Secondary Substations	Nr. 700
• End Users	Nr. 65.000
• Production plants connected to the LV Distribution Grid	Nr. 1400
• Max Peak Power	58 MW
• Max "reverse" Peak Power	22 MW

Figure 1: Main features of Terni Power Grid.

The substations are distributed on the territory of the Municipality of Terni following the concentration of homes, businesses, and enterprises on criteria related to consumption and production of energy, which is mainly from PV power plants (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Overview Terni Power Grid; a) Substation distribution, b) Users and Power Plant distribution.

In the recent years, MV/LV distribution grids have been increasingly powered internally by Renewable Energy Sources (RES). This means that a Power Grid designed to be a passive grid, i.e. fed from the High Voltage (HV) National transmission Grid, has had to cope with large internally generated power flows that have caused congestion and losses due to Reverse Power Flow (RPF) at Secondary Substation (SS) and Primary Substation (PS) level (Figure 3). This change has also necessitated the development and implementation of grid

management mechanisms that are more and more dependent on advanced Information Technology (IT) tools. These applications facilitate Demand Response (DR) by users and enable them to consume energy when production from RES is greatest.

Figure 3: Energy Consumption and Energy production in the Grid.

2.2 Terni’s Energy Demand

On the whole, every year inside the distribution grid of Terni is produced about half of the energy necessary to its needs (Figure 4). A non-negligible part of this self-produced quota is produced by photovoltaic plants with intermittent and seasonally variable functioning.

Figure 4: Overview of the Terni Power Grid energy mix.

2.3 Reverse Power Flow

Generally, balancing the grid based solely on managing consumption flexibility with DR is not sufficient and therefore storage systems must also be employed to smooth out power peaks and reduce RPF. These solutions must also take into account the increasing proliferation of Electric Vehicle (EV) charging stations. The value of energy is no longer tied only to the cost of production, but also to when it is produced and consumed. The flexibility of producers and consumers is a great added value for the safe and reliable management of a modern distribution grid (Smart Grid). In Terni’s power grid, the amount of energy that should be stored and returned when needed to eliminate RPF is 3-6 GWh/month (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Overview of the Terni Power Grid monthly self produced energy.

Reducing RPF in the distribution grid makes energy management more sustainable. Consuming energy when there is more production from fluctuating renewable sources makes the power grid more reliable and resilient because it reduces congestion and overloads that are a cause of failure. The Italian pilot with the implementation of a hybrid AC/DC grid in a real distribution grid aims to achieve these results and validate them from a DSO perspective.

3 Pilot Set Up

3.1 Pilot Introduction

The Italian Pilot consists of a 700 VDC section embedded in a portion of the existing LV AC distribution grid of Terni (Figure 6). The DC bus-bar is fed through two AC/DC converters each connected to a different SS. The SS involved in the pilot are called SCOV and ASM.

Figure 6: Italian Pilot in the Terni's Distribution Grid.

The Italian pilot uses a large portion of the AC distribution grid to host the new unipolar 700 VDC unipolar distribution section. The main DC components are two LV AC converters to power the DC bus-bar (Figure 7). The DC distribution includes a storage system, a PV power plant, an EV vehicle charging station, and a power distribution for priority loads.

Figure 7: Overview diagram of the Italian Pilot.

3.2 Use Cases

3.2.1 Forming an Energy Community

Energy Communities are promoted by the Renewable Energy Directive RED II (EU, 2018), in which the definitions of collective self-consumption among members of an apartment block or building and Renewable Energy Community (REC) are given. This European Directive stipulates that members must produce energy for their own consumption and that the energy produced can be shared among users using existing distribution grid. In Italy, the RED II has recently been transposed into national legislation by Legislative Decree nr.199 (Italy, 2021). According to this Legislative Decree, in Italy, each Energy Community can install RES with a total power not exceeding 1MW and all members of the Community must be connected to the same PS of the distribution grid. In the Italian pilot, an energy community is simulated in a portion of the grid where a hybrid AC/DC grid is installed. In this portion of the LV grid there are AC and DC users, RES and storage.

The main purpose of the energy community is to share self-generated energy among the members of the community. The Italian pilot DC energy community cannot work disconnected from the grid, i.e., operating only in island mode. The REC must be always connected to the grid in order to receive at any time the energy when the community cannot satisfy with its own energy sources its energy needs and vice versa to give back to the grid the surplus of energy produced. Another important feature of the energy community is black start, i.e., the ability to self-power critical users in the event of the absence of the main grid, as described in Deliverable D8.1 Sections 3.1.3 and 3.1.4.

The main goal of the REC is to maximize the self consumption of energy to reduce the request and cost of energy supplied by the grid. However, efficient and coordinated management between the REC and DSO, without limiting self-consumption, can help increase grid efficiency through, for example, the reduction of RPF in SS (Figure 8).

Figure 8: RPF and self consumption in HYPERRIDE district.

The relationship between the DSO and the DC REC in this Use Case is based on the vision of the DC section implemented in HYPERRIDE as a whole (Figure 9). In this Use Case, all the components of the DC energy community are managed by a local management system provided by EATON.

Figure 9: Renewable Energy Community - Use Case 1.

The local DC management system will acquire the operational data from the converters and DC devices implemented in the Pilot. The new equipment to be installed in the Italian Pilot are listed below:

- Nr. 2 AIT Active Front End (AFE) Smart Grid Converters which provide full functionality towards the AC side, including low voltage ride through and base functions towards the DC side (Figure 10). These AC/DC converters are fed by SSs via insulation transformers for a galvanic insulation between the AC and DC sections. The power rating of each AFE converter is 35 kW.

Figure 10: AIT Smart Grid Converter as basis for 34.5 kW LV DC Active Front End.

- Nr.2 Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converters 40 kW, 750 V (Figure 11). It is a bidirectional converter. It provides various modes of operation and is used for energy storage and EV charging applications in the pilot. It interface the DC grid with the EATON Battery Energy System and the EMOT EV Charging System. It was originally planned to deploy a 50kW bidirectional DC-DC converter for the charging station to be installed in Italian pilot, however it was decided to opt for Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 40kW, 750V since the cost is three times lower than 50kW solutions and, therefore, they are not cost-

effective. Considering the infrastructure of the pilot, this modification does not imply a change in the expected results of demonstration activities; nevertheless, it will facilitate the integration activities with the DC grid control system since the converter of the storage system and the EV charging system will be the same.

Figure 11: Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 40 kW for Battery Energy System.

- Nr.1 Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 25 kW, 800 V (Figure 12). It is a bidirectional converter. It provides various modes of operation and is used for the solar arrays that in the demonstrator is directly connected to the DC bus-bar.

Figure 12: Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 25kW for solar arrays.

- Nr.1 Zekalabs RedPrime AC-DC Converter 25 kW, 800 V (Figure 13). It is a bidirectional converter. It provides various modes of operation and in the pilot is used to supply the AC critical load.

Figure 13: Zekalabs RedPrime AC-DC Converter 25kW for AC critical loads.

The local EATON DC Control System will manage the operations of the equipment in the DC REC to maximize the self-consumption inside the community.

3.2.2 Provide Flexibility to DSO

Flexibility is the modification of generation injection and/or consumption patterns in reaction to an external signal (price signal or activation) in order to provide a service within the energy system. The parameters used to characterize flexibility in electricity include; the amount of power modulation, the duration, the rate of change, the response time, the location etc. The main services related to the flexibility of a customer connected to the hybrid AC/DC grid of the pilot in Terni are:

- DR is a voluntary changes by consumers or producers of their usual electricity flow patterns in response to market signals such as time variable prices or incentives.
- PV Power smoothing consisting in storing PV extra production (defined as difference between the power produced by PV system and load of the facility) in order to maximize the consumption of energy produced by local RES and reduce RPF in SS.
- Peak shaving is the flattening of an electricity consumption load curve and is closely linked to DR.
- EV flexible charging service is performed by increasing as much as possible the self consumption share of renewable power or when cheap electricity is available, e.g., from high renewable power production at times when the demand is low and sufficient grid capacity allows for providing the required charging power by local RES.

All these ancillary services can be performed by the hybrid AC/DC distribution grid interfacing the local EATON DC control system with the LV AC Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system, which is based on the system platform WONDERWARE. The communication protocol to interface the control systems is MODBUS protocol, in this case too. Data and information exchange between DC and AC grids are bidirectional. All the equipment installed for this Use Case is the same in the previous Use Case nr. 1. This Use Case is implemented and tested in the process based on the DC devices response to a Resolution Plan (RP) issued by the DSO as for demand of ancillary services (Figure 14). The Resolution Plan takes into account the grid state forecast and sets the requirements to the DC distribution section to supply services to the grid within the range of its flexibility. In the Italian pilot, these services are tested and evaluated in the hybrid AC/DC distribution grid context.

It will be also interfaced with the existent SCADA of the LV AC distribution grid.

3.2.3 Efficient Fault Management in Grid Operation

The implementation of the hybrid AC/DC grid in a LV distribution grid make it possible the parallelization of LV feeder from different sources. Double power supply is a redundancy that increase the reliability of the system. The hybrid AC/DC grid and in particular the DC bus-bars fed by a double power line coming from different SS can be classified as preferential loads with a major level of security in terms of uninterrupted power system. For this, each DC bus-bars have a great resilience to face physical fault and cybernetic attack. This feature is ensured by an automation system that can vary operation according to operating or fault conditions. The architecture of the platform is designed to be in compliance with the Cybersecurity requirements for an IT infrastructure serving an Electrical Power and Energy System (EPES). The efficient

Figure 14: Provide Flexibility to DSO.

fault management in the power grid guarantee the higher level of availability possible in the specific fault condition. In the Power grid, the management and analysis of faults is currently carried out in the MV grid by means of the SCADA system supplied by SIEMENS. It provides a complete solution for monitoring, remote control, and automation of HV and MV electrical distribution grids, as well as HV/MV PS and MV/LV SS. In this Use Case, the state of the grid in relation to the fault is evaluated as a whole by a joint analysis with the state of the hybrid part of the grid. For this reason, both the local LV systems DC and AC will be interfaced with the SCADA system that manages the MV grid at the higher level (Figure 15). In the Italian pilot, this use case will be used to evaluate the failure rate benefit of a hybrid grid powered by two different SS.

The best grid set-up, following faults, is driven by automated supervisory and remote-control systems (SCADA, LV System Platform, DC control system). Protection devices, such as circuit breakers and relays, that detect faults by measuring currents and voltages, belong to a separate system from remote-control because it must have less latency times and higher reliability level.

Figure 15: Efficient Fault Management in Grid Operation.

For this reason, the DC control system does not include protection coordination and selectivity as described in Deliverable D8.1 Section 3.2. These capabilities are covered by the DC circuit breakers implemented in the LV DC section. The new protection devices implemented in the Pilot for the DC section are sized to ensure the highest level of selectivity. The requirements for the selection of the circuit breakers have been:

- to allow the elimination of the fault in the shortest possible time and to avoid interruptions in the parts of the circuit not affected by the fault.
- to prefer the use of components already available on the protection market for economy and interoperability, since the pilot is the real model of a hybrid distribution grid.

During the implementation of the pilot and the execution of the tests, innovative protection systems, of interest for HYPERRIDE partners, will be experimented.

4 Pilot Test Bed

4.1 Physical Pilot Overview

As described in previous sections of this document, although the new components are located in a small area of the LV grid, a large portion of the grid, starting from the PS, will be analyzed for Use Cases studies and evaluation of the impact of testing on the grid as a whole. In this larger portion, particular operating conditions will need to be simulated to highlight the outcomes of each Use Case. It is necessary to make simulations because, unlike the DC portion where there are users suitable for experimentation, the grid involved in the Pilot is a real grid on which are connected real users who cannot suffer interruptions and reductions in the quality level of service that would have a negative impact on their lives or activities. The three cases are listed in order of increasing complexity, regarding the involvement of the power grid.

The Use Case 1 (Forming an Energy Community) represents the DC section as an Energy Community and the control of the equipment is strictly local (EATON DC Control System) with a monitoring system confined only to DC equipment. The only information exchanged is with the RPF for the prediction of power demand to the LV AC grid.

The Use Case 2 (provide flexibility to the DSO) represents the core of the LV DC/DC hybrid distribution grid. This use case extends the relationships of the DC active and passive users to the LV AC distribution grid. The two supervisory and control systems of the DC and AC grids interact to exchange the necessary data for the REC to provide ancillary services to the distribution grid. In this Use Case, the perimeter of the concerned grid widens including the low voltage distribution grid belonging to two SS.

The Use Case 3 (Efficient Fault Management in Grid Operation) represents the top level in involving the physical infrastructure of the power grid. The simulation of faults in the MV grid with the assessment of the impact on the LV AC/DC hybrid grid will involve all the supervisory and control systems of the grid:

- SIEMENS STM SCADA System;
- WONDERWARE LV AC System Platform;
- EATON DC Control System.

In this simulation, failure conditions will be simulated and appropriate countermeasures will be implemented to limit the effects on the LV AC/DC hybrid grid.

For a correct view of the Italian Pilot, it is therefore necessary to identify the complete distribution grid. Among the three PSs present in the ASM power grid, the one that constitutes the HV power supply connection of the Pilot is the PS named EX-SIT (Figure 16). It is a substation fed in HV at 120 kV with three HV/MV 120/20 kV transformers having a rated power of 20-18 MVA.

From EX-SIT starts the MV line that feeds a chain of seven SSs in an operating configuration called "enter-exit" until it reaches the power feeding points of the SSs that are part of the LV AC/DC hybrid grid. The seven SSs are listed below:

- DEPURATORE;
- NUOVA SICMA;
- SICMA;

Figure 16: "EX SIT" Primary Substation in the Italian Pilot.

- GLOBO;
- PICCHIO SALLO;
- CELI;
- MAZZOCCHIO.

Each Secondary Substation is powered by two separate power lines, so PICCHIO SALLO and CELI feed SCOV and MAZZOCCHIO feeds ASM which is also directly powered by EX-SIT as second power line (Figure 17). In this Pilot operating configuration, the MV distribution mesh is circularly closed by two different power lines that both start and finish at the PS.

Figure 17: MV Power Grid with the chain of Secondary Substations involved in the Italian Pilot.

SCOV and ASM are the SSs that both feed the 700 VDC section through two AFE converters (Figure 18). The grid configuration adopted for the 700 VDC section allows the Pilot to maintain the same level of power redundancy normally provided in the traditional AC distribution system. This solution keeps the reliability of the hybrid grid high.

Figure 18: LV AC/DC Hybrid Distribution Grid with SCOV and ASM Secondary Substations.

The overall scheme of the entire distribution grid is shown in Figure 19 where the measure points are indicated and numbered as monitoring nodes.

At the measurement points of the grid, the electrical parameters: active power (P), reactive power (Q) (only for AC sections of the grid), voltage (V) and current (I) are monitored. The selection of the measurement points is made for the study of the Power Flow of the grid and they concern (Figure 20):

- electrical lines entering or leaving the PS;
- power lines entering or leaving the SS;
- consumption of MV users;
- consumption of LV users;

For LV consumption, the measurement is carried out by means of smart meters installed at the customers' premises; in this case, the electrical parameters in the node are calculated by aggregating the consumption of each user connected to that node.

Figure 19: Complete diagram of the Italian Pilot- From HV to 700 VDC bus-bars.

4.2 DC Distribution Grid Multi-phase Diagram

The DC section is new to the distribution grid, thus, it requires a specific design, not only for the converters discussed above but also for the electrical panels and circuit wiring. The executive design starts with the multi-wire diagram shown in Figure 21.

In order to select the DC protection devices: fuses or DC circuit breakers, an analysis was done to identify the best solution for the demonstrator. In conclusion, it was opted to use DC circuit breakers. This solution offers better operational management of the pilot and good reliability

Figure 20: AC monitoring point of the grid.

due to the miniature DC circuit breakers available as standard products on the market. The demonstrator may also be used to test LV solid-state switches. The value of 700 VDC requires caution in circuit breakers wiring that maintain the rated breaking capacity valid for this DC voltage level if the poles are placed in series as shown in the multi-wire diagram (Figure 21).

The diagram may change as a result of ongoing activities in other HYPERRIDE WPs where the basic functionality of converters and new equipment are still in development stage. Measurements of DC values are made by converters that allow real-time measurement of significant electrical parameters such as voltage and current. The measure point in the DC section of the hybrid AC/DC grid are listed below.

- P17, P18 - AIT AFE AC-DC Converter 35 kW, 750 V;
- P19 - Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 40 kW, 750 V;
- P20 - Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 25 kW, 800 V;
- P21 - Zekalabs RedPrime DC-DC Converter 40 kW, 750 V;
- P22 - Zekalabs RedPrime AC-DC Converter 25 kW, 800 V.

The possibility of using DC meters with appropriate characteristics to implement fiscal measures is under evaluation. During testing on the Pilot, it will be possible to deploy DC smart meters to validate their use on a hybrid LV AC/DC distribution grid. Interest in developing such devices from HYPERRIDE partners is being verified. The use of low-cost metering devices developed by third parties is not ruled out, since in a hybrid distribution grid there would be a need to have fiscal measures for DC users.

4.3 Measurement Points in the Pilot

In order to effectively sum up what has already been reported regarding the measurements at the base of the tests that will be performed in the pilot, the characteristics of the various mea-

Figure 21: Multi-wire diagram with new AC-DC Equipment implemented ex-novo in the Italian Pilot.

surement points and the applicable Use Case for each of them are summarized in Figure 22. The measurement points are identified by the progressive numbers shown in the complete diagram (Figure 19).

MV measurements are acquired in the field from existing or newly installed meters that will take voltage and current values from already installed voltage and current transformers.

LV measurements will be executed by suitably installed balance meters for the Italian Pilot experimentation.

Point	Measure	Voltage	Substation	UC1	UC2	UC3
P1	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	EX-SIT	X		
P2	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	EX-SIT	X		
P3	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	EX-SIT	X		
P4	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	DEPURATORE	X		
P5	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	0,4 kV	NUOVA SICMA	X		
P6	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	SICMA	X		
P7	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	GLOBO	X		
P8	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	PICCHIO SALLO	X		
P9	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	0,4 kV	PICCHIO SALLO	X		
P10	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	CELI	X		
P11	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	0,4 kV	CELI	X		
P12	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	0,4 kV	MAZZOCCHIO	X		
P13	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	0,4 kV	SCOV	X	X	
P14	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	SCOV	X	X	
P15	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	0,4 kV	ASM	X	X	
P16	P,Q,I1,I2,I3,V	20 kV	ASM	X	X	
P17	P,I,V	700VDC	DC SECTION	X	X	X
P18	P,I,V	700VDC	DC SECTION	X	X	X
P19	P,I,V	700VDC	DC SECTION	X	X	X
P20	P,I,V	700VDC	DC SECTION	X	X	X
P21	P,I,V	700VDC	DC SECTION	X	X	X
P22	P,I,V	700VDC	DC SECTION	X	X	X

Figure 22: Measurement points list of the Italian Pilot.

Figure 24: Use Case topics.

modern distribution grid must have in the context of a hybrid LV AC/DC grid.

5 Conclusions

The set-up of the Italian Pilot was defined starting from the needs of a real distribution grid in which the component of self-produced energy from RES is very high and in the coming years will be increasingly so.

Following the needs of a real grid, a new DC distribution section has been designed and proposed. This structure is aimed at evaluating the contribution that the hybrid LV AC/DC could give to the traditional architecture.

The new grid implementation in the Italian Pilot takes place exclusively in the LV distribution section. Within the LV DC section the constitution of an REC of exclusive DC users and producers is assumed. For REC new management models are implemented and a new grid architecture is realized to increase environmental sustainability by promoting self-consumption and information exchange with the DSO for RPF reduction in the District. By connecting DC section with the existing AC distribution one, the hybrid grid takes shape and possible ancillary services that the hybrid part of the grid can provide to the DSO are analyzed.

The vision of the distribution grid as a whole, starting from a PS that is the point of connection to the National Transmission Grid, is confirmed in the evaluation of service continuity by analyzing the possible benefits that a hybrid AC/DC grid can give to the whole system in the presence of failures at all levels of the grid. At the latter point, given the large-scale involvement of a real grid, field experimentation will remain for only the LV portion of the distribution grid involved in the Pilot. The fault conditions that might arise for the MV portion of the grid will be simulated, always keeping in mind the possible real conditions that could occur. More detailed analysis for the experimentation in the Italian pilot are in progress and could give the pilot more support and facilitate the application of the concepts already expressed in this Deliverable, which remains valid constituting the guidelines to be adopted.

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